

PECULIARITIES OF STYLISTIC DEVICE OF SIMILE IN I.YUSUPOV’S AND BYRON’S POETRY

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Annotation: The article deals with the language peculiarities of poetry, using similes in poetry. Bright, original similes in the poetry of People’s poet of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan, Hero of Uzbekistan poet I.Yusupov and well known poet of English people Byron are comparatively investigated in the article.

Izoh. Maqolada she’riyatning til xususiyatlari, she’rda o‘xshatishlar qo‘llanishi haqida so‘z boradi. Maqolada O‘zbekiston va Qoraqalpog‘iston xalq shoiri, O‘zbekiston Qahramoni shoiri I.Yusupov va ingliz xalqining taniqli shoiri Bayron she’riyatidagi yorqin, o‘ziga xos o‘xshatishlar qiyosiy o‘rganilgan.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются языковые особенности поэзии, использование сравнений в поэзии. В статье сравнительно исследуются яркие, самобытные сравнения в поэзии народного поэта Узбекистана и Каракалпакстана, Героя Узбекистана поэта И.Юсупова и известного поэта английского народа Байрона.

Key words: Stylistic device, simile, poem, image-building.

Ключевые слова: Стилистический прием, сравнение, стихотворение, создание образа

Kalit so'zlar: Stilistik trop, o‘xshatish, she’r, obraz yaratish

Similes help to create images in poetry. Writers can give a new or surprising meaning to an object when they compare it to something familiar. The similes forcibly set one object against another regardless of the fact that they may be completely alien to each other. And without our being aware of it, the simile gives rise to a new understanding of the object characterizing as well as of the object characterized.

In the article we’ll try to analyze similes in the poetry of People’s poet of Uzbekistan and Karakalpakstan I.Yusupov and well known poet of English people Byron.

No definition can comprise all the inner qualities of the object and new combinations of it with other objects as well. A deeper penetration into the anthology of the object will always reveal some hither to unknown qualities and features. In simile one can find that one of the qualities of the object in question is made to sound essential. The quality picked out may be seemingly unimportant, and it is frequently transitory, but for a special reason it is elevated to the greatest importance and made

into a telling feature. Simile – is one of the wide – spread emotive language means, which exists from the time of Homer, so that a great attention was paid to it in ritorika. J.Muton considers that nothing but simile reveals spiritual and intellectual life of an author, allows penetrate into mysteries of subconscious [1,107].

In I.Yusupov’s s poetry simile is widely used for the purpose of image-building. The poet for comparison his heroes uses the most various sources for image-building. We’ve analyzed some examples from I. Yusupov’s poetry, where simile is brightly used. Especially in I.Yusupov’s poetry we’ve observed bright original similes for describing nature phenomenon, vivid characterization of his personages. For instance: Sumliq qilsa sir aldirar baladay,

Kewilsheklik minezine kuyemen
Al endi onin ken jaziyra daladay
Azamatliq ken peyilin suyemen.

(“Qaraqalpaqti kop maqtama kozimshe “ 9b)

In these stanzas perfect character of Karakalpak people compared with the child’s and their kind heartedness is compared wide fields. So gives bright colour to the description

Otirispada eske tussen nagaybil
Ismin tirilmese misali bir gul
Jaqsin ilinbese tilge sol gezde;
(“Sorsha” 22b)

In these stanzas the name of human being is compared with a flower. Comparison human being with plants especially with flowers undoubtedly creates bright image.

Let’s investigate next stanzas
Doslarim sizlersiz kewlim hosh bolmas
Barimiz bir bagdin bulbillerimiz
Sizden bolek ilham magan yosh bolmas
Nanday putin igbalimiz, jerimiz.
(“Tashkentli shayir doslarima”27b)

In this poem the friends- poets are compared with nightingale. Their fortune and land – with bread. The comparison with food usually gives brightness to the description.

Men dunyani jas kelindey jasartip,
Xasil lipas penen kiyindiremen
(“Men pahtakesh xaliqpan”28b)

The world is compared with a young brideroom who dressed with rich silk dress.

Ayaz qala-danaliqtin qalasi
 Gone tariyx sagan iyek suyegen
 Qiyratiwshi waqit penen talasip
 Tas burkittey turisindi suyemen. (“Ayaz qala”49b)

Using genuine simile poet describes the historical place Ayaz qala imaginatively, comparing it with a stone eagle.

I.Yusupov as the source of comparison often uses such sources as roze, nightingale, fruit, animal kingdom, plants and inanimate objects. In the next example the day is compared with rich harvest of an apple.

Хәм кетгим жумысқа жүрип жалма-жан,
 Болды кернеп талўас, жигерим-күшим,
 Күним, сени мол жемисли алмадай,
 Инсаний мазмунға толтырмақ ушын... (Bugingi ku'n 110b)

In addition to, the hardworking people of Karakalpakstan is compared to animal kingdom to be exact with the elephant as far as everyone knows that elephants are strong, patient, hardworking and kind animal.

Хеш кимде жоқ сениң мийнеткешлигин,
 Пилдей парасатың, зәбердеслигин.
 Балғадан қаймықпас палўан төслигим,
 Абырайға тырысқыш дана халықсаң.(Sen mardana haliqsa'n')

In Byron's poetry simile is widely used for the purpose of image-building. The poet for comparison his heroes uses the most various sources for image-building.

Let's investigate some examples from Byron's poetry, where simile is brightly used.

For sometimes they contain a deal of fun
 Like mourning coaches when the funeral's done. (Beppo p.373).
 In this example habits of people compared with inanimate things.
 I said that like a picture by Giorgione
Venetian women were, and so they are.(Beppo p.371)
 The beauty of venetian women is compared with a picture of Giorgione.
 Our bread was such as captives' tears
 Have moistened many a thousand years
 Since man first pent his fellow men
 Like brutes within an iron den: [2,358]

These stanzas drew our attention with its originality. We have never expected that bread would be compared with captives' tears. And actions of man is compared with brutes. So was built a bright image.

So feeble now-his mother’s softness crept
So those wild eyes, which like an infant’s wept: [2,349]

Man’s eyes and infant’s weep, these are different kind of things are compared.
So gives bright colour to the description.

Byron addresses to the ocean:

A shadow of man’s ravage, save his own,
When, for a moment, like a drop of rain,
He sinks in to thy depths with bubbling groan,
Without a grave, unknelled, unciffined, and unknown.[2,376]

In these stanzas simile (like a drop of rain) helps to strengthen the tragedy. This example deeply impresses a reader with its expressiveness

The result of investigation shows that Byron and I.Yusupov uses similes to produce more intense emotional impact on the reader and promote better understanding the personages. The analyses of vast practical data [105examples] shows that stylistic device of simile in the most universal means of describing people’ appearance, characterizing personages for revealing their feelings, their inner world and their relationship.

Literature:

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